

Consent

Dear Participant,

Our research group is currently performing a study on the prevalence and impact of non-inclusive or discriminatory language in Software Engineering artifacts and developer communications. We would be grateful if you could participate in our survey, which consists of a short background questionnaire, and reviewing and responding to a list of identified non-inclusive terms. There will also be an opportunity to contribute to our list if you have encountered any additional terms not included in the survey.

The survey should take no more than 10-15 minutes of your time. Your identity will not be recorded and your responses will be strictly anonymous.

Your decision to take part in this research study is entirely voluntary.

Submission of the survey will be interpreted as your informed consent to participate and that you affirm that you are at least 18 years of age.

If you have any questions about the research, please contact Ahmad Tayeb at tayeb@cs.fsu.edu, or the faculty advisor Dr. Sonia Haiduc at shaiduc@cs.fsu.edu. If you have any questions regarding your rights as a participant in a research project, contact the FSU Institutional Review Board (IRB) at (850) 644-7900 or via email at humansubjects@fsu.edu.

Please feel free to print or save a copy of this page for your records.

*I have read the above information and agree to participate in this research project.
If you would like to participate, please access the survey by using the button below.

Demographics

Which of the following best describes your primary occupation?

- Undergraduate Freshman/Sophomore
- Undergraduate Junior/Senior
- MS Student
- PhD student
- Faculty
- Professional Software Developer
- Other (Please specify)

How much programming experience do you have in your primary occupation?

- No experience
- Less than 1 year
- 1-5 years
- 6-10 years
- More than 10 years

What is your gender?

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Prefer to self identify

What is your age?

- 18-24
- 25-31
- 32-38
- 39-45
- 46-52
- 53-59

60 or older

What is your ethnicity?

Asian / Pacific Islander

Black or African American

Hispanic or Latinx

Native American

White

Other

Is English your native language?

Yes

No

What is your country of origin?

What is the country you currently reside in?

List of Terms

We have identified the following list of potentially non-inclusive or discriminatory language commonly used in Software Engineering artifacts (source code, documentation, issue reports, etc.) and software developer communication.

Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:

I find the following terms are non-inclusive or discriminatory:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Whitelist/Blacklist	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Master/Slave	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Grandfathered	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Gendered nouns (Guys, Ladies, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Gendered pronouns (he/him/his, etc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sanity check	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Man hours	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Dummy value	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please share your reasoning for selecting "Strongly Disagree", "Disagree" or "Neither Agree nor Disagree" in the question above.

- My native language does not share the negative connotations of the terms
- My culture does not share the negative associations of the terms
- I do not believe that these terms have impact in the context of software
- These terms do not have a personal impact on me or my associates
- Other

Please list any other discriminatory language you have encountered in Software Engineering artifacts or in software developer communications that was not listed above.

Term Usage

Which terms are frequently used in your software projects?

- Whitelist/Blacklist

- Master/Slave
- Grandfathered
- Gendered nouns (Guys, Ladies, etc.)
- Gendered pronouns (he/him/his, etc)
- Sanity check
- Man hours
- Dummy value
- Other
- None of the above

Do you or your teams use any of the following alternative terminology in your software projects?

- Whitelist/Blacklist alternatives (Allowlist/Blocklist, etc.)
- Master/Slave alternatives (Leader/Follower, etc.)
- Grandfathered alternatives (Legacy status, etc.)
- Gender neutral nouns (folks, etc.)
- Gender neutral pronouns (they, ze, etc.)
- Sanity check alternatives (coherency check, etc.)
- Man hours alternatives (work hours, etc.)
- Dummy value alternatives (placeholder value, etc.)
- Other
- None of the above

Impact

Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:

Non-inclusive or discriminatory terminology used in software artifacts and software developer communications like the one listed in the this survey has negatively impacted the following aspects of my life and work environment:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Diversity in my team's composition	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Inclusion and acceptance of diverse ideas at work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My self-esteem	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My work productivity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My sense of belonging in an organization	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please share your reasoning for selecting "Strongly Disagree", "Disagree" or "Neither Agree nor Disagree" in the question above.

- My native language does not share the negative connotations of the terms
- My culture does not share the negative associations of the terms
- My company's culture does not share the negative associations of the terms
- I do not believe that these terms have impact in the context of software
- These terms do not have a personal impact on me or my associates
- Other

Please list any other ways discriminatory language has negatively impacted your life and work environment.

Final Thoughts

Please share any additional thoughts you may have on discriminatory language in Software Engineering artifacts or in software developer communications.

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